

IMPROVING STUDENTS' LEXICAL COMPETENCE BY USING VISUAL MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

Visual media is one of the most effective tools for teaching a foreign language. This article discusses the methodology of increasing students' vocabulary using this tool.

INTRODUCTION

Unfortunately, many students do not master lexical units when studying a particular topic, but simply memorize for the sake of assessment long lists of isolated words offered by the authors of English textbooks at the end of each cycle/module. Practicing teachers admit that they often encounter situations in the classroom, when generating their own statements, the studied vocabulary is not remembered, students experience great difficulty in combining lexical units, pauses are prolonged, and emotional tension increases. Meanwhile, it is no secret that the more associative connections a particular word acquires in the students' heads, the higher the prerequisites for the formation of a flexible lexical skill (i.e., students' independent choice of lexical units to solve a particular communicative task).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modernization of modern language education requires finding effective ways to intensify the process of teaching a foreign language. Psychologists say that if a student is busy with an interesting activity, then he can work for a long time, without breaks, without getting tired. And, conversely, if the student is not interested in the lesson, despite the expenditure of great effort on the part of the teacher, the learning process is psychologically rejected by the student, makes him nervous and quickly tires him.

The use of information technology and Internet services in English lessons has a number of advantages. Thanks to the implementation of the principle of visualization in teaching, key words are quickly memorized, figurative memory training, brainstorming, analysis of the main ideas of a text read or listened to, and activation of schoolchildren's background knowledge (obtained in literature, history, geography, music lessons) [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let us dwell in more detail on the use of a computer program to create a "word cloud" in an English lesson and show some working techniques for developing the communicative

competence of students at different levels of education. There are several programs for creating “word clouds”, for example: <http://worditout.com>, <http://wordle.net>, <http://www.tagxedo.com>, <http://www.abcy.com>, www.tagul.com, where you just need to enter the site URL in a special field, and the program independently generates a “cloud”, displaying the most frequently used words in large font. In this case, you can change the background color, font type and shade.

Using the example of one of the web services, we will show how to create a “word cloud”. So, the Tagul service requires registration ('sign up'), after which a letter with a password and a link to work on this web page will be sent to your mailbox. The operating algorithm is as follows [2]:

1. click on the “create a new cloud” button;
2. enter the name of the cloud (cloud 1);
3. load words or text (Import words). If you need to save phrases, then all words are entered in a column. You can work with each word separately: change the size, color, rotation angle, font;
4. choose a “cloud” shape – those offered by the site’s author or create your own image (shape);
5. change the general font if we want for all words (fonts). You can make all words in capital letters, small letters or capitalize (UPPER, lower, Capitalize);
6. change the arrangement of words and color scheme (layout);
7. save the finished “cloud” (save changes);

This methodological technique, used to firmly memorize vocabulary and process foreign language texts, is very convenient and especially useful for visual learners (those who perceive most of the information with the help of visual support). On the one hand, a visual image of the keywords of any text is created in an attractive form. On the other hand, students’ associative thinking develops. The “word cloud” technique can be used when systematizing vocabulary, at the stage of repeating language material introduced in previous lessons, to facilitate the memorization of foreign words, and to reconstruct coherent texts. It can be:

Exercises to improve auditory and pronunciation skills

- **imitation exercises** – repetition of difficult-to-pronounce words and memorization of their spelling (for example, the names of the countries that make up Great Britain (Fig. 1): Great Britain, England, Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland):

CONCLUSION

Key words recorded in one picture are used as verbal supports of stimuli that help students to easily restore the general meaning of a read/listen text (reconstruct a sample text) or retain in memory their own monologue utterance within the framework of the lexical topic being studied. This is one way to teach schoolchildren to logically and consistently formulate thoughts orally and in writing. Using the “word cloud” service allows the teacher to diversify the learning process, make it more attractive, thereby increasing the effectiveness of learning and promoting the formation of sustainable positive motivation of students for the subject “English” in general.

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